

Pattern of Mobile Phone Use in Children Diagnosed with Neuro-Developmental Disorders: A Retrospective Cross Sectional Study

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Neuro-developmental disorders, Use of Mobile Phone.

Abstract

Background: Digital technologies including mobile phone device have progressively become an integral part of the life of children and adolescents for communication as well as learning and playing. According to some authors, the use of mobile device constitutes a “passive” behavior or one-way communication, which takes the child away from other more useful learning processes.

Objectives: To evaluate the pattern of mobile device use in children with Neurodevelopmental disorders in Bangladesh.

Methods: This retrospective cross sectional type of study was conducted at Department of Paediatric Neurology, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU) from November 2022 to April 2023. Children aged 1-5 year with neurodevelopmental disorders eg; ASD, ADHD, Isolated speech delay, Epilepsy, GDD were selected and enrolled in this study. Then children were assessed thoroughly by taking detailed history and physical examination. Neurodevelopmental assessment was done by Rapid Neurodevelopmental Assessment (RNDA). In confirmed cases, parents were asked retrogradely regarding the pattern of use mobile phone of their child. Data were collected in pre-designed structured questionnaire after taking approval of Institutional review board. An informed written consent was taken from the parents or the legal guardians.

Results: Total 100 children were included. Male were outnumbered (71%) than female. Isolated speech delay was the commonest neurodevelopmental disorder (33%) followed by ASD. Average screen used time were about 3-5 hours of one-third children (38%). Majority of the parents (42.4%) were involved in their household work at the time of mobile use. More than half of the children (57.8%) use mobile phone for watching cartoon. About 50% parents believe that mobile phone having decremental effect on child’s brain development. Maternal mobile was the prime source (65.5%) for using mobile device.

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Conclusion: Isolated speech delay was the most commonly encountered neurodevelopmental disorder in this study. Average screen used time were about 3-5 hours for one-third studied children. More than half of the neurodevelopmental disordered children use mobile phone for watching cartoon. About half of the parents believe that mobile device have definite decremental effects on child's brain development.

Introduction

Neurodevelopment is an overlapping inter-connection between genetic, neural, cognitive, emotional and behavioural processes across the developmental milestone. Development is a continuous process. It is more important in early childhood period (0-8 years). Significant and persistent disruption of this process through environmental and genetic risk factors can lead to neurodevelopmental disorders. According to WHO prevalence of Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is 1 in every 160 children, Epilepsy is 4–10 in every 1000 children and Cerebral palsy is 3-4 in every 1000 children [1].

Common neurodevelopmental disorders in children are ASD, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), cerebral palsy, learning disabilities, intellectual disability, Epilepsy and isolated speech & language disorders. Children with neurodevelopmental disorders present difficulties with speech & language, motor skills, behavior, memory, learning, or other neurological functions. Though the symptoms and behaviors of neurodevelopmental disorders usually change as child grows older, but some disabilities become permanent. Diagnosis and management of these disorders are very difficult for physicians [2].

Nowadays, digital technologies have progressively become an integral part of the life of children and adolescents for communication as well as learning and playing. Particularly, the "intuitive" technology of the new digital tools (e.g., smartphones and tablets) is very enchanting and greatly induces the interest of younger children that with a single touch with finger, can access screens, images, videos, and sounds [3]. Application of this tools and accessibility of videos in internet provide interactive content that costs effective to the caregiver, so use of these devices are becoming increasingly common in households [1].

Digital tools act as a two-way sword. They offer the children many learning opportunities. On the other side, they lead to risks like delays in some cognitive, linguistic and social skills. According to some authors, the use of mobile device constitutes a "passive" behavior or one way communication, which takes the child away from other more useful learning processes [3].

So, it is our interest to evaluate the pattern of mobile phone use in children with neurodevelopmental disorders. Considering it as the one of the burning issue in the current time and the increasing rate of use of

mobile phone among children, this area should to be carefully explored as a preventable risk factors.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective cross sectional type of study was conducted at Department of Paediatric Neurology, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU) from November 2022 to April 2023. Children aged 1-5 year with diagnosed neurodevelopmental disorders eg; ASD, ADHD, Isolated speech delay, Epilepsy, GDD were selected and enrolled in this study. Children with motor impairment (cerebral palsy, down syndrome), hearing impairment and development epileptic encephalopathy were excluded from this study. Then children were assessed thoroughly by taking detailed history and physical examination. Neurodevelopmental assessment was done by Rapid Neurodevelopmental Assessment (RNDA). In confirmed cases, parents were asked retrogradely regarding the pattern of use mobile phone of their neurodevelopmentally challenged children. Total 100 children were included of both sexes. Data were collected in pre-designed structured questionnaire. Institutional review board approved this study. In addition, an informed written consent was taken from the parents or the legal guardians. Data were presented in tabulated form. Data were analyzed using computer based program Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for Windows version 23.

Operational Definitions

ASD: The Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) represent a wide spectrum of associated cognitive and neurobehavioral deficits, including deficits in socialization and communication, with restricted and repetitive patterns of behaviors.

Epilepsy: Epilepsy is a brain disorder that causes recurring, at least two unprovoked seizures occurring more than 24 hours apart.

Global developmental delay: Significant delay in two or more developmental domains.

ADHD: Persistent pattern of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity that interferes with functioning or development.

Intellectual disability: Neurodevelopmental disorders that begin in childhood and are characterized by intellectual difficulties as well as difficulties in conceptual, social, and practical areas of living.

Isolated Speech Delay: In children with language delay, who doesn't have any neurological or genetic cause.

Rapid Neurodevelopmental Assessment (RNDA): RNDA is an assessment tool designed to ascertain

functional status in nine domains: primitive reflexes, gross and fine motor development, vision, hearing, speech, cognition, behavior and seizures [4].

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Age (In years)	Minimum	Maximum
	2	15
Mean ±SD	5.35 ±3.18	
Sex (n=100)	Frequency	Percentage
Male	71	71
Female	29	29
Residence (n=100)	Frequency	Percentage
Urban	25	25
Rural	75	75
Social Classes (n=100)	Frequency	Percentage
Lower	28	28
Middle	70	70
Upper	02	02
Consanguinity (n=100)	Frequency	Percentage
Present	11	11
Absent	89	89
Perinatal Events ^a (n=36)	Frequency	Percentage
PNA	16	44.4
LBW	09	25
Prematurity	06	16.7
Hyperbilirubinemia	04	11.1
Sepsis	01	2.8

Note: ^a Multiple response was noted

Table 1 shows the mean age of the patients were 5.35 (±3.18) years. Majority of them were male (71%). 75% of them belonged to urban residence. Maximum (70%) patients belonged to middle social classe. Majority of them had no consanguinity (89%). PNA was among the major among perinatal event (44.4%)

Table 2 Shows Majority of study participants had isolated speech delay (33%)

Table 2. Type of Neurodevelopmental Disorder Among Study Participants (n=100)

Type of neurodevelopmental disorder	Frequency	Percent
ISOLATED SPEECH DELAY	33	33
ASD	31	31
ADHD	19	19
ID	17	17

Table 3. Association of Types of Perinatal Event with Types of Neurodevelopmental Disorders

Type of perinatal event	Type of neurodevelopmental disorder				p value ^a
	Isolated speech delay	ASD	ADHD	ID	
PNA n(%)	4 (25)	2 (12.5)	2 (12.5)	8 (50)	<0.05
LBW n(%)	3 (33.3)	2 (22.2)	0(0)	4(44.4)	>0.05
Prematurity n(%)	1(16.7)	1(16.7)	1(16.7)	3(50)	>0.05
Hyperbilirubinemia n(%)	3 (75)	0(0)	0(0)	1(25)	>0.05
Sepsis n(%)	0(0)	1(100)	0(0)	0(0)	>0.05

Note: ^a p value was measured by Fischer-exact test

Table 3 shows Majority (8/16, 50%) of study participants with ID had history of PNA (p<0.05).

Figure 1 shows majority (38%) of study participants use mobile phone about 3-5 hours and 37% children use mobile phone about 2-3 hours

Figure 1 Average Time of Using Mobile Phone in Hours (n=100)

Table 4. Type of Parenteral Belief Regarding Mobile Phone use (n=100)

Parenteral beleif	Frequency	Percent
Benificiary	9	9.0
Decremental	50	50.0
No comments	41	41.0

Table 4 shows most of the parents believed using mobile phone had decremental effect on child’s brain development.

Table 5. Time of Mobile Use by Children Relation with Parents (n=100)

Time of mobile use by children relation with parents	Responses ^a	
	Frequency	Percent
During Household work	70	42.4
While feeding	63	38.2
Before sleeping	29	17.6
For Pacifying/Like Toys	2	1.2
For others purpose	1	0.6

Note: ^a Multiple response was noted

Table 5 shows most of the time children use mobile phone during the household work by their parents (70, 42.4%).

Table 6. Source of Use Mobile Phone by Child (n=100)

Source of use mobile phone by children	Responses ^a	
	Frequency	Percent
Used by mother	74	65.5
Used by father	27	23.9
Used by family member	8	7.1
Other source of use	4	3.5

Note: ^a Multiple response was noted

Table 6 Shows source of use mobile phone by children mostly from their mother (74, 65.5%).

Table 7. Pattern of Use Mobile Phone by Children

Pattern of use mobile phone by children	Responses ^a	
	Frequency	Percent
Watching Cartoons	78	57.8
Listening to music	24	17.8
You tube/Watch movies	20	14.8
Playing video games	12	8.9
For others purpose	1	0.7

Note: ^a Multiple response was noted

Table 7 shows watching cartoons (78, 57.8%) was the major pattern of mobile phone use by the study participants.

Discussion

Environment may modify the epigenome of the differentiating cell, leading to changes in the human brain and contribute to neurodevelopment [5]. Mobile device, a modifiable environmental factor has brought some blessings in the modern era. Although the device also has some disadvantages as well specially in early periods of childhood development. Screen dependency has regarded as one of the contributing factor and an additional burden to the neurodevelopmental disorder. Evidence suggested that chronic sensory stimulation via excessive screen exposure might had detrimental effect on brain development [6].

Here the study was conducted among 100 children. There was male predominance (71%). Although most of them were from rural residence (75%) and belonged to middle class family (70%). A study in China suggested boys and rural residents were especially vulnerable to negative effects of device use [7].

Arora et al reported the most common neurodevelopmental disorder was hearing impairment and ID [8]. Although there was a bit difference with the current study findings where Isolated speech delay was the commonest (33%) followed by ASD. The difference probably related to the variation in sampling method and type of neurodevelopmental disorder in included sample and tools used to assess this neurodevelopmental disorders.

The average estimated time spent in mobile media in this study was around 3-5 hours. Lin et al observed that between 2-5 years of age with a neurodevelopmental disorder the average screen time was 3.98 hours, and 93.9% of them exceeding 1 hour of screen time daily [9]. The study findings support the current study. Another study by Coutinho et al, reported among all the neurodevelopmental disorders children with ASD had the largest time spent with the mobile device (>3 hours) but others had lesser time with mobile [1]. The variation in age at sampling with different cultural aspects may attribute to a bit difference with the current study.

In this study About half of the parents (50%) believe to had a decremental effect of mobile phone on children and a few of them believed to had a beneficiary effect (9%). Zarei et al., found significant association of increase call time and usage of mobile phone with speech disorder in children [10]. These findings support the current belief. Although Al-Rashaida et al., suggested that that mobile devices can be successfully utilized in educational programs targeting communication, academic, and social skills [11]. This study supported with the belief of beneficiary effect.

The study found most of the mobile phone had been used during the household work by parents (42.4%) followed by feeding (38.2). Another study found 58% of the mobile phone was given during feeding¹. Thus, feeding and household chores were the prime time of mobile device use as part of distractors.

Most of the children in the studied subjects used mobile phone for watching cartoons as part of their recreation (57.8%). Jenaro et al., stated that young people with disabilities made more social and recreational rather than educational use of these tools, and show higher rates of excessive use of in comparison to young people without disabilities [12]. Although the current study did not have a comparison group but recreational use of the device was evident as well.

The study was a single centre study with a small sample size. There was no such study in our country like this before. It may impart additional knowledge to the current understanding about neurodevelopmental disorder that may help in the management.

Conclusion

Isolated speech delay was the most commonly encountered neurodevelopmental disorder in this study. Average screen used time were about 3-5 hours for one-third studied children. More than half of the neurodevelopmental disordered children use mobile phone for watching cartoon. About half of the parents belief that mobile device have definite decremental effects on child's brain development.

Limitations and Recommendation

Limitation of this study is a cross sectional and single centre study. Furthermore, device use has been a burning issue with its positive and negative detrimental aspects specially in these age group. But new multi centered longitudinal study with a comparison group on a larger sample may be conducted to draw an appropriate conclusion.

Conflict of Interest

There was no conflict of interest.

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Author Contributions

Study design and data analysis: Professor Dr. Gopen Kumar Kundu.

Data collection: Dr Sadia Sultana

Clinical help : Dr Arbab Sarker

Review:Dr Farah Naz Dola , Dr Sharmina Afrin Sheemu

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